

Special Relativity and Information

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In a previous note (1) we attempted to derive Newton's second law $d/dt p = F(x) = -dV/dx$ for a conservative force using information ideas alone. In this derivation we implicitly treated m_0 , the rest mass, as a constant. In this note we focus on the situation of special relativity in the presence of a function $V(x)$ which is independent of time, but changes the speeds of particles as they pass through space.

In (1) we used the idea that $d/dt \rightarrow v(x) d/dx$ and assumed $v(x)=dx/dt$ with dx being constant and $dt(x)$ as representing information. We linked $V(x)$ which changes particle velocities to $v(x)$ which is variable and changes through $d/dt v(x)$ which we equated with $C dV/dx$ so that there was minimum information for an equilibrium result. Using $d/dt \rightarrow v(x)d/dx$ this leads to a form: $.5v(x)v(x) + C V(x) = \text{constant}$ which is equivalent to Newton's conservation law if the constant C and constant are chosen properly.

To consider the special relativistic situation we consider a single particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$ and then view it from a moving frame with constant speed $-v$. We argue that a person in the frame sees x',t' such that $x'/t'=v$. We also argue that there should be an energy E and momentum defined by $p=Ev/bb$ where b is constant which becomes as we argue c the speed of light. From these ideas we show that $E=m_0cc$ in the rest frame and $E= m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ in the moving frame. We note that in the limit of $v/c \ll 1$, $E= m_0cc + .5movv$ with the second term being exactly the result obtained using informational ideas and a constant m_0 i.e. Newton's results. We try to account for this in the next paragraph.

We then use the notion of $p(x)$ instead of $v(x)$ as "information" so that the extra $m=m_0/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ information is incorporated. We argue that for fixed dx values $p(x)$ changes because $dt(x)$ changes and so we use information to define: $d/dt p(x) = C dV/dx ((A))$. This is the force law in special relativity (2) if $C=-1$. WE argue that both $(d/dx, d/dt)$ and $(p, E-V)$ represent 4-vectors and so one may take the dot product using the metric $(1,-1)$ Yielding: $pp + (-E+V)(-E+V) = \text{constant} = mom_0cc$. In the nonrelativistic limit this yields $.5movv + V(x) = E_0$. We argue that the Newtonian information is also of the form of a Lorentz dot product i.e. $d/dt v(x) = CdV/dx = -C d/dx (E_0+m_0-V)$ so the dot product of $v(x)v(x) - (E_0+m_0-V)(E_0+m_0-V)$ with $m_0 \gg E_0-V$ yields the $.5movv$ form.

Newton's Case

In (1) we considered trying to derive Newton's second law (and its conservation of energy form) by using only information arguments. We implicitly assumed rest mass m_0 is a constant and argued that $V(x)$ (a potential) is the only fixed x information in the system. We further argued that in equilibrium other information dependent on x must combine to yield a function directly linked to $V(x)$. We choose $v(x) = \text{velocity}$ as this function. In statistical mechanics one may directly link $-\ln(\text{density}(x))$ to $C V(x)$, but in the Newtonian case we argue that x dependence enters through $dt(x)$ for fixed dx such that $v(x) = dx/dt(x)$. Thus $dt(x)$ changes in each constant dx unit. We thus suggest using:

$d/dt v(x) = C dV/dx$ ((1)) so that both sides contain changes.

In other words $d/dt \rightarrow v(x)d/dx$ is a weighted translational shift generator in space. ((1)) is in the form of Newton's second law and using $d/dt \rightarrow v(x)d/dx$ leads to a conservation type law:

$.5v(x)v(x) - CV(x) = \text{constant}$ ((2)) which ultimately becomes conservation of energy.

We then ask: How does one modify this to account for special relativity?

Special Relativistic Considerations

Consider the information contained in a scenario with a particle at rest at $x=0$ with rest mass m_0 at $t=t_0$. Next consider this system as seen from a frame moving at a constant speed $-v$. The new x', t' should satisfy $x'/t' = v$ and there should now be energy $E(v)$ and momentum p defined as $E(v)v$ in the system. Originally there was only rest mass so we equate that with $E(v=0)$ and $p=0$. We note that x and p seem to be on the same footing i.e. are both 0 in the rest frame as $v=x'/t'$ creates p . Given $v=x'/t'$, one may consider a symmetric matrix transforming $(x=0, t_0)$ i.e.

$$\begin{vmatrix} G(v) & vG(v) \\ vG(v) & G(v) \end{vmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

Then $x' = vG(v)t_0$ and $t' = G(v)t_0$ so $x'/t' = v$. We assume that the same matrix transforms (p, E) because these are really created by changes in x' and t' which lead to v . Then: $E = G(v)m_0 b$ where b is a constant and $p = vE/(bb)$ which is the definition of p i.e. energy flux up to a multiplicative constant.

Given that a particle in a rest frame is physically the same even if viewed from a constantly moving frame one would assume some kind of conservation law to represent this idea. We suggest the modulus of (p, E) , but this cannot be taken as $pp+EE$ because this becomes larger and larger with increasing v . Rather we use $EE-pp = EE(1-vv/bb)$ and link it with $m_0 b$. This yields $E = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ if $b=c$ the speed of light.

Why should $b=c$? We argue that the matrix ((2)) should also apply to (p, E) for light and this leads to $b=c$.

As a result, we see that the information $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ represents a particle with constant v . If $v(x)$ then $p(x)$ is the information not $v(x)$ as in the case of m_0 (i.e. the Newtonian case considered in (1)).

Information and Special Relativity

One may now attempt to use information to establish a special relativistic law linking $V(x)$ and $p(x)$ instead of $v(x)$. Given that $V(x)$ is a function of x we still divide the x axis into constant dx units. $v(x) = dx/dt(x)$ so each dx unit is linked to a different weight $dt(x)$ as in the Newtonian case, but there is also the $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ weight as well in p . Thus we suggest:

$$d/dt p(x) = -dV/dx C \quad \text{where } C \text{ is a constant} \quad ((3))$$

with $p(x) = mv/\sqrt{1-v(x)v(x)/c^2}$. We note that $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ is the special relativistic result given in (2). For a conservative Force we use $F = -dV/dx$.

Special Relativistic Energy Relation

Unlike the Newtonian case: $d/dt \rightarrow v(x)d/dx$ does not lead to a form which may be immediately integrated to give an energy result. Rather one must use the idea of dot products. Consider the Lorentz invariant (dot product) $A = -Et + px$. Then $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ and $dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E$. As seen in a moving frame, these results should hold using prime values so we suggest that $(d/dx, d/dt)$ transforms as a 4-vector. (Other arguments such as the dot product of $(d/dx, d/dt)$ and (x, t) may be used.)

This means that in ((3)) p and $E - V$ where E is constant total energy such that $dE/dx = 0$ should be 4-vectors. This leads to the idea of an invariant:

$$(E - V)(E - V) - pp = \text{constant} \quad ((4))$$

One may set this constant equal to $m_0 c^2$. Thus $E - V(x)$ is the free particle energy at each x .

Link with Newtonian Mechanics i.e. the Nonrelativistic Case

One may note that the nonrelativistic case which assumes $m_0 = \text{constant}$ leads to a conservation of energy equation of the form:

$$.5mv^2 + CV(x) = \text{constant} \quad \text{or} \quad .5m_0 v^2 + V(x) = \text{energy} \quad (\text{excluding rest mass energy})$$

Thus the form $.5mv^2$ appears from strictly informational arguments.

On the other hand special relativistic arguments given above which were not linked to information in the same way yielded:

$$E \text{ free particle with rest mass} = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} = m_0 c^2 + .5m_0 v^2$$

Why do these two different approaches yield the same factor $.5mv^2$?

We argue that it is linked to the idea that: $d/dt v(x) = C dV/dx$ in the Newtonian approach is of the form of a Lorentz invariant, in that d/dt and d/dx are parts of an exact 4-vector and $v(x)$ and $E_0 + m_0 V(x)$ (E_0 constant $dE_0/dx = 0$) are approximate (nonrelativistic) parts of the real p, E . Thus $v(x)v(x) + CC(m_0 + E_0 - V)(m_0 + E_0 - V) = \text{constant} = m_0^2 c^4$ ($c=1$). Assuming $m_0 \gg E_0$ and V as well leads to: $v(x)v(x) + CC 2m_0(E_0 - V) = 0$ or Newton's conservation form. This same approach

may be applied to the nonrelativistic limit of ((4)). Thus the basic Lorentz dot product is already found in Newton's second law which may be formulated using informational arguments.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that one may use similar information arguments used in (1) to develop Newton's second law. The difference which occurs is that $v(x)$ is not the only piece of variable x information in the system. There is also $m_0/\sqrt{1-v(x)v(x)/c^2}$. Thus one should consider $p(x) = m_0v/\sqrt{1-vv/c^2}$ as the variable information type piece in a problem with a potential $V(x)$. $p(x)$ changes for fixed dx units because $dt(x)$ so there is a different weight in each dx piece. Thus we suggest using d/dt to describe changes in $p(x)$ which are equated to dV/dx multiplied by a constant. $V(x)$ is a fixed piece of x information and $p(x)$ may adjust so that it does not represent new information, consistent with constraints in the system i.e. the changing $dt(x)$. This leads to:

$$dp(x)/dt = d/dt m_0v/\sqrt{1-vv/c^2} = F(x) = -dV/dx \text{ as given in (2).}$$

We note that the informational change form d/dt on the LHS and d/dx on the RHS is linked to the 4-vector $(d/dx, d/dt)$. In the Newtonian case it is seen that $d/dt v(x) = C dV(x)/dx$ leads immediately to a conservation of energy form using $d/dt \rightarrow v(x)d/dx$ i.e. $.5v(x)v(x) - CV(x) = \text{constant}$. Interestingly the term $.5v(x)v(x)$ also arises directly from special relativity i.e. from an expansion of $m_0/\sqrt{1-vv/c^2}$ for $v/c \ll 1$. We argue that this is the case because Newton's second law is already in the "form" of a Lorentz invariant i.e. $(d/dt, d/dx) \cdot (m_0v(x), m_0 + E_0 - V(x))$ where $E_0 = \text{constant}$ excluding rest mass. Thus one may also take the dot product of $m_0v(x)$, $E_0 + m_0 - V(x)$ which yields $.5m_0vv + V(x) = E_0$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Newton's Second Law In Terms of Information (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Relativistic_mechanics